

Using the Open Science Framework for data storage

What is the Open Science Framework ?

The [Open Science Framework \(OSF\)](#) is an open-source platform to manage, share, and publish your research outputs—from documenting your study design and planning methods, through data collection and analysis, to final publication and dissemination. It can function as a collaborative workspace, enables you to preregister your research project and makes your study discoverable.

What is the Open Science Framework not ?

The OSF is **not designed** as a data repository and does **not** meet the standards that exist for good long-term data archiving. Many of the features that would guarantee long-term data preservation and make a dataset FAIR are either missing altogether or entirely optional. Because of this, there are various reasons why the OSF is **not suited for long-term archiving or publishing of research data**. Moreover, in most cases there are better alternatives available for researchers, in particular the [Radboud Data Repository](#) or the [DANS Data Stations](#).

The primary reason why the OSF does not meet the requirements of a trustworthy data repository is the lack of long-term preservation planning. In other words, it is unclear how the OSF will guarantee continued access to the data for the entire timeframe during which research data must be preserved. The [Terms of Service, Article 10](#) state:

The OSF, at its sole discretion, however, reserves the right at any time and from time to time to modify, suspend, discontinue, or terminate the Websites or Services or portions thereof with or without notice. You agree that we will not be liable to you or to any third party for any modification, suspension, discontinuation, or termination of the Websites or Services.

There also exist other limitations:

	The OSF	Radboud Data Repository	DANS Data Stations
Size limits	50 GB	Unlimited	50 GB (more with support)
Persistent identifier (PID)	Optional	Assigned and reserved	Assigned and reserved
Metadata	Optional	Follows metadata standards	Follows metadata standards
Licensing	Optional	Mandatory	Mandatory
Internal archiving	Without PID	With PID	Only restricted with no access
Restricted access	Not really	Yes	Yes
Personal data	No	Yes	Yes
Sensitive data	No	Yes	Yes
Institutional affiliation	No	University and research institute affiliation	University affiliation
Audit trail	No	Yes	Yes
Expert curation	No	Yes	Yes
Versioning	Only file versioning	DOI versioning	DOI versioning

What to consider before you upload data to the OSF ?

The OSF website can safely be used for project management, preregistration and reporting of research project findings. However, **it is recommended that you contact your local data steward before you use the OSF for the archiving and publishing of research data.** Your data steward can advise if the OSF is indeed the best solution, or if a better alternative exists for your research field and the type of data that you are working with.

What to do when you upload data to the OSF ?

If you have consulted your data steward and together have decided that OSF is indeed the best platform to publish the data, there are some critical steps that you must take in order for the dataset to comply with the [GDPR](#), [Radboud University RDM policy](#) and the [FAIR principles](#).

Safety precautions

- ❖ **Follow the OSF [Terms of Service, Article 10](#), and backup all data and content archived or published on the OSF on other Radboud University approved storage locations in order to avoid unwanted loss of data.**
- ❖ Go to Settings – Account settings – Default Storage Location and select “Germany – Frankfurt” so that the research data is stored in an EU jurisdiction.
- ❖ Make sure that there are no personal or sensitive data in your dataset, and seek advice from a [privacy officer](#) if you are not sure.
- ❖ Make sure that you are following the [Guidelines on control of research data](#) and that the Radboud University can act on this control, for example by giving access to your OSF collection to the data steward of your research institute.
- ❖ **Before switching your collection from “private” to “public”, ask your data steward to review your OSF Data Archive to make sure that it is sufficiently FAIR and does not accidentally contain personal or sensitive data.**

How to make your data on the OSF FAIR

- ❖ The OSF allows you to upload data as part of a generic project, but also as a registration in the [OSF Data Archive](#). This last option is strongly recommended, as this encourages you to use the OSF “Data Archiving and Sharing Template” with relevant metadata. Making an OSF Data Archive allows you to receive a Digital Object Identified (DOI) which you can use in publications, and which allows you to register your dataset (see point further below).
- ❖ Fill in [all the metadata fields](#), making sure to include as much information as possible so that re-users can really understand the context and content of your data collection.
- ❖ Include sufficient documentation in your collection to make it possible for someone else to understand the background of the research project, the structure of the files and folders, and the variables, codes, software, scripts, and other information that is presented in the data.
- ❖ When selecting a [license](#), make sure that you understand how this choice might affect the potential reuse of your data.
- ❖ Understand that the OSF is **not** affiliated with the Radboud University, which means that it will be difficult to find your research data without access to the [DOI of your registration](#). It is therefore strongly recommended that you manually register your dataset in the [Current Research Information System](#) of the university so that it can be found.